

WORK DONE BY:

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I have the impression that some scientists, perhaps moved by the enthusiasm to explore ideas that verge on the magical, have departed - albeit momentarily - from the rigor that characterizes scientific thought. Added to this is the gratification they receive from their readers or audience, who, amazed by what is presented to them, tend to accept these ideas with almost blind faith, trusting more in the prestige of the person presenting them than in the solidity of the evidence. The problem is aggravated when many of these readers or listeners are not scientists, and end up adopting as truth statements that, in reality, lack support.

Worse still, those who believe in these ideas tend to spread them with enthusiasm, which gives rise to a chain of disinformation that begins to build, little by little, a body of beliefs that is presented as knowledge, but which is not science. Once that happens, reversing the process becomes extremely difficult - if not impossible - because the damage has already become deeply rooted, both in public perception and in the culture.

True scientific progress must be based on solid and verifiable foundations, not on speculations with no factual basis. When we build our knowledge on fanciful premises, we divert valuable resources and efforts, hindering the genuine advancement of knowledge. Science evolves effectively only when it is based on verifiable evidence and rigorous methodologies.

What we are going to try in this text is to demonstrate that there is nothing magical in the results obtained by measuring what happens at the subatomic level with particles that separate each one with its real characteristics.

We will review the demonstration of the inequality and our intention is to conclude, contrary to what has always been said, that the inequality is always fulfilled and consequently the results obtained in the experiments can be explained starting from reality with its hidden variables.

It is nice to think that nature can behave in strange ways such as the fact that when we observe something, that something “decides” at that moment what it is going to become (superposition state); or also to think that when a change occurs in something, this change will cause something, say light years away to change instantaneously (entanglement).

Obviously this is going to attract many people to be interested in physics, however it would not be honest to maintain this fact as true since we would be building on a false fact and consequently everything that is built on this foundation may turn out to be equally false.

What was the intention of John Bell's inequality to demonstrate?

The intention was to demonstrate whether or not there is a reality that causes the results obtained in practice or whether these facts resulting from the experiments are inexplicable in the sense that they do not correspond to reality but to something magical.

REASONS TO QUESTION AN ACCEPTED TRUTH

I want to state how I agree with the process that has tried to demonstrate that the famous hidden variables that imply a reality that explains the phenomenon that has been observed through experiments do not exist.

Bell's inequality is in my opinion a genius as an idea to demonstrate whether or not hidden variables exist. That is, it allows to have a comparative framework that serves as a tool for this purpose.

The problem is with the experiments.

In order to accept the experiments as a proof that hidden variables do not exist, it is necessary that all particles "participate" in the test. That is, that all particles are detected, which is not the case. In the experiments only a minimum part are detected and there are others that claim to have detected 80% of them.

To illustrate my idea about the failure of experiments I will take as an example the experiment carried out in 2015.

In the 2015 Hanson experiment conducted at Delft University, the detection efficiency was approximately 85% to 90%, depending on the measurement channel. The percentage of undetected photons (or events) was in the range of 10% to 15%.

This is a high level of detection however it can be shown that it is not sufficient to demonstrate that John Bell's inequality was not satisfied.

(POSSIBLE) HIDDEN VARIABLES THAT DEMONSTRATE THAT A HIGHER LEVEL OF DETECTION IS REQUIRED TO ACCEPT THIS EXPERIMENT AS VALID.

My way of demonstrating this is simple. I will provide a set of possible hidden variables and at the same time I will simulate certain levels of detection lower than those indicated from 10 to 15 % finding that the estimated values are reached with which Bell's inequality is supposedly broken. I will then provide a second set of different possible hidden values that led me to the same result of minimum detection percentages at which the values of the experiment are reached and which are lower than those of the experiment itself.

We start with the following values for the experiment:

$$E(a,b) = 0.7358$$

$$E(a',b) = 0.5949$$

$$E(a,b') = 0.4838$$

$$E(a',b') = -0.6078$$

The following tables shows for each of the values shown the hidden variables and how the above values can be reached even with a higher level of detection than indicated in the article on the 2015 experiment:

HIDDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A1B1	1,000	864	13.6%
0.099	1	1	1	1	0.099	0.115	1	99	99	0
0.096	1	-1	1	-1	0.096	0.111	1	96	96	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.091	1	1	-1	-1	0.091	0.105	1	91	91	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.123	-1	1	1	-1	0.123	0.000	-1	123	0	123
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.127	-1	1	1	-1	0.127	0.132	-1	127	114	13
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.159	1	1	-1	-1	0.159	0.184	1	159	159	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.154	1	-1	1	-1	0.154	0.178	1	154	154	0
0.151	1	1	1	1	0.151	0.174	1	151	151	0
E(a, b)	0.50	0.50	0.50	-0.50	0.500	0.736		1,000	864	136

VARIABLES OCULTAS	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2
0.099	1	1	1	1
0.096	1	-1	1	-1
0.000	-1	1	-1	1
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1
0.091	1	1	-1	-1
0.000	1	-1	-1	1
0.123	-1	1	1	-1
0.000	-1	-1	1	1
0.000	-1	-1	1	1
0.127	-1	1	-1	-1
0.000	1	-1	-1	1
0.159	1	1	-1	-1
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1
0.000	-1	1	-1	1
0.154	1	-1	-1	-1
0.151	1	1	1	1

E(a, b)	0.50	0.50	0.50	-0.50
---------	------	------	------	-------

N	n
0.099	0.106
0.096	0.102
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.091	0.097
0.000	0.000
0.123	0.130
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.127	0.135
0.000	0.000
0.159	0.169
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.154	0.100
0.151	0.160

0.500	0.595
-------	-------

A1B2
1
-1
1
-1
1
-1
1
-1
1
-1
1
-1
1
-1
1
-1
1

1,000	940	6.0%
99	99	0
96	96	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
91	91	0
0	0	0
123	123	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
127	127	0
0	0	0
159	159	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
154	94	60
151	151	0
1,000	940	60

HIDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2
0.099	1	1	1	1
0.096	1	-1	1	-1
0.000	-1	1	-1	1
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1
0.091	1	1	-1	-1
0.000	1	-1	-1	1
0.123	-1	1	1	-1
0.000	-1	-1	1	1
0.000	-1	-1	1	1
0.127	-1	1	-1	-1
0.000	1	-1	-1	1
0.159	1	1	-1	-1
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1
0.000	-1	1	-1	1
0.154	1	-1	-1	-1
0.151	1	1	1	1

E(a, b)	0.50	0.50	0.50	-0.50
---------	------	------	------	-------

N	n
0.099	0.103
0.096	0.099
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.091	0.094
0.000	0.000
0.123	0.127
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.127	0.131
0.000	0.000
0.159	0.164
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.154	0.141
0.151	0.141

0.500	0.484
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A2B1
1
1
-1
-1
-1
-1
1
1
1
1
-1
-1
-1
-1
1
1
1

1,000	969	3.1%
99	99	0
96	96	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
91	91	0
0	0	0
123	123	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
127	127	0
0	0	0
159	159	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
154	137	17
151	137	14
1,000	969	31

HIDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2
0.099	1	1	1	1
0.096	1	-1	1	-1
0.000	-1	1	-1	1
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1
0.091	1	1	-1	-1
0.000	1	-1	-1	1
0.123	-1	1	1	-1
0.000	-1	-1	1	1
0.000	-1	-1	1	1
0.127	-1	1	-1	-1
0.000	1	-1	-1	1
0.159	1	1	-1	-1
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1
0.000	-1	1	-1	1
0.154	1	-1	-1	-1
0.151	1	1	1	1

E(a, b)	0.50	0.50	0.50	-0.50
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N	n
1000	933
0.099	0.035
0.096	0.103
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.091	0.098
0.000	0.000
0.123	0.131
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.127	0.137
0.000	0.000
0.159	0.170
0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000
0.154	0.165
0.151	0.161

-0.500	-0.608
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A2B2
1
-1
1
-1
-1
1
-1
1
1
1
-1
-1
-1
-1
1
1
1

1,000	933	6.7%
99	32	67
96	96	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
91	91	0
0	0	0
123	123	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
127	127	0
0	0	0
159	159	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
154	154	0
151	151	0
1,000	933	67

Now, in relation to the same 2015 experiment, I will show another example of possible hidden variables, with the interesting feature that if the real hidden variables were similar to this example, it would be necessary that the loss of particles in the experiments should not be greater than 1%. In other words, their detection rate would have to be greater than 99% for the experiment to be credible:

HIDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A1B1	1,000	990	1.0%
0.137	1	1	1	1	0.137	0.139	1	137	137	0
0.092	1	-1	1	-1	0.092	0.093	1	92	92	0
0.002	-1	1	-1	1	0.002	0.002	-1	2	2	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.159	1	1	-1	-1	0.159	0.160	1	159	159	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.004	-1	1	1	-1	0.004	0.000	-1	4	0	4
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.135	-1	1	1	-1	0.135	0.130	-1	135	129	6
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.165	1	1	-1	-1	0.165	0.167	1	165	165	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.158	1	-1	1	-1	0.158	0.160	1	158	158	0
0.148	1	1	1	1	0.148	0.150	1	148	148	0
E(a, b)	0.72	0.50	0.35	-0.43	0.500	0.736		1,000	990	10

HIDDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A1B2	1,000	940	6.0%
0.137	1	1	1	1	0.137	0.146	1	137	137	0
0.092	1	-1	1	-1	0.092	0.038	-1	92	36	56
0.002	-1	1	-1	1	0.002	0.002	1	2	2	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.159	1	1	-1	-1	0.159	0.169	1	159	159	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.004	-1	1	1	-1	0.004	0.004	1	4	4	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.135	-1	1	1	-1	0.135	0.144	1	135	135	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.165	1	1	-1	-1	0.165	0.176	1	165	165	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.158	1	-1	1	-1	0.158	0.164	-1	158	155	4
0.148	1	1	1	1	0.148	0.157	1	148	148	0
E(a, b)										
	0.72	0.50	0.35	-0.43	0.500	0.595		1,000	940	60

HIDDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A2B1	1,000	909	9.1%
0.137	1	1	1	1	0.137	0.151	1	137	137	0
0.092	1	-1	1	-1	0.092	0.101	1	92	92	0
0.002	-1	1	-1	1	0.002	0.002	-1	2	2	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.159	1	1	-1	-1	0.159	0.115	-1	159	104	54
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.004	-1	1	1	-1	0.004	0.004	1	4	4	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.135	-1	1	1	-1	0.135	0.149	1	135	135	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.165	1	1	-1	-1	0.165	0.142	-1	165	129	37
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.158	1	-1	1	-1	0.158	0.174	1	158	158	0
0.148	1	1	1	1	0.148	0.163	1	148	148	0
E(a, b)										
	0.72	0.50	0.35	-0.43	0.500	0.484		1,000	909	91

HIDDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A2B2	1,000	887	11.3%
0.137	1	1	1	1	0.137	0.155	1	137	137	0
0.092	1	-1	1	-1	0.092	0.104	-1	92	92	0
0.002	-1	1	-1	1	0.002	0.002	1	2	2	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.159	1	1	-1	-1	0.159	0.179	-1	159	159	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.004	-1	1	1	-1	0.004	0.004	-1	4	4	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.135	-1	1	1	-1	0.135	0.152	-1	135	135	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.165	1	1	-1	-1	0.165	0.186	-1	165	165	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.158	1	-1	1	-1	0.158	0.178	-1	158	158	0
0.148	1	1	1	1	0.148	0.039	1	148	35	113
E(a, b)										
	0.72	0.50	0.35	-0.43	0.500	-0.608		1,000	887	113

Finally, I present an additional example based on an arbitrary value of $Z = 2.121$, which clearly violates Bell's inequality but can be justified by possible values of hidden variables. In a real experiment, the maximum percentages of undetected particles that should not be exceeded are: 0.1%, 1.0%, 4.0%, and 8.7%. These values, along with the probabilistic distribution of undetected particles, were obtained using an optimization model I developed. If there is interest in learning more about it, I would be happy to share it.

HIDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A1B1	1,000	999	0.1%
0.119	1	1	1	1	0.119	0.119	1	119	119	0
0.090	1	-1	1	-1	0.090	0.090	1	90	90	0
0.020	-1	1	-1	1	0.020	0.020	-1	20	20	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.089	1	1	-1	-1	0.089	0.089	1	89	89	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.091	-1	1	1	-1	0.091	0.091	-1	91	91	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.131	-1	1	1	-1	0.131	0.131	-1	131	131	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	-0.001	1	0	-1	1
0.158	1	1	-1	-1	0.158	0.158	1	158	158	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.154	1	-1	1	-1	0.154	0.154	1	154	154	0
0.149	1	1	1	1	0.149	0.150	1	149	149	0
E(a, b)	0.52	0.56	0.47	-0.42	0.517	0.517		1,000	999	1

HIDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A1B2	1,000	990	1.0%
0.119	1	1	1	1	0.119	0.121	1	119	119	0
0.090	1	-1	1	-1	0.090	0.091	-1	90	90	0
0.020	-1	1	-1	1	0.020	0.020	1	20	20	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.089	1	1	-1	-1	0.089	0.090	1	89	89	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.091	-1	1	1	-1	0.091	0.091	1	91	91	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	-0.002	-1	0	-2	2
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.131	-1	1	1	-1	0.131	0.133	1	131	131	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.158	1	1	-1	-1	0.158	0.153	1	158	152	6
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.154	1	-1	1	-1	0.154	0.153	-1	154	151	2
0.149	1	1	1	1	0.149	0.151	1	149	149	0
E(a, b)	0.52	0.51	0.47	-0.42	0.512	0.516		1,000	990	10

HIDDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A2B1	1,000	960	4.0%
0.119	1	1	1	1	0.119	0.124	1	119	119	0
0.090	1	-1	1	-1	0.090	0.094	1	90	90	0
0.020	-1	1	-1	1	0.020	0.020	-1	20	20	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.089	1	1	-1	-1	0.089	0.051	-1	89	49	40
0.000	1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.091	-1	1	1	-1	0.091	0.094	1	91	91	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.131	-1	1	1	-1	0.131	0.137	1	131	131	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.158	1	1	-1	-1	0.158	0.164	-1	158	158	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.154	1	-1	1	-1	0.154	0.160	1	154	154	0
0.149	1	1	1	1	0.149	0.156	1	149	149	0
E(a, b)	0.52	0.51	0.47	-0.42	0.468	0.529		1,000	960	40

HIDDEN VARIABLES	A1B1	A1B2	A2B1	A2B2	N	n	A2B2	1,000	913	8.7%
0.119	1	1	1	1	0.119	0.036	1	119	32	87
0.090	1	-1	1	-1	0.090	0.099	-1	90	90	0
0.020	-1	1	-1	1	0.020	0.021	1	20	20	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.089	1	1	-1	-1	0.089	0.097	-1	89	89	0
0.000	1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.091	-1	1	1	-1	0.091	0.099	-1	91	91	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	-1	1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.131	-1	1	1	-1	0.131	0.144	-1	131	131	0
0.000	1	-1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.158	1	1	-1	-1	0.158	0.173	-1	158	158	0
0.000	-1	-1	-1	-1	0.000	0.000	-1	0	0	0
0.000	-1	1	-1	1	0.000	0.000	1	0	0	0
0.154	1	-1	1	-1	0.154	0.168	-1	154	154	0
0.149	1	1	1	1	0.149	0.164	1	149	149	0
E(a, b)	0.52	0.51	0.47	-0.42	-0.424	-0.559		1,000	913	87

I invite anyone who likes to perform their own calculations to verify those performed in this work and at the same time I invite anyone who likes to send me results of other experiments indicating the level of detection and I will gladly apply my methodology to find the minimum level of detection for hidden variables that I will propose.